

DESIGN SELECTION METHODOLOGY FOR COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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SUMMARY: This paper presents a methodology to help designers select a shortlist or optimum design of composite structure from a large number of alternatives, taking into account conflicting design objectives or constraints (e.g. weight and cost). The methodology is based on creating a database containing results from an exhaustive search of a wide range of possible solutions. These results can be viewed using a commercial software selection package, originally written for materials selection. The designer then has freedom to change the selection criteria and required design constraints, to allow interactive selection of the data. The design methodology is illustrated by way of a case study, the design of a reinforced dogbone specimen.

KEYWORDS: design, structures, finite element analysis, optimisation.

INTRODUCTION

Rapid advances in finite element (FE) methods have allowed their use as part of an optimisation strategy for design of composite structures. The route pursued by most researchers has been to use numerical optimisation strategies in conjunction with FE methods. While these are valuable where a single objective can be defined, they are less useful where there are conflicting design objectives (e.g. minimum weight and cost). Here graphical presentation of performance criteria allows designers to improve their 'feel' for a problem, leading to refinement in the design constraints and further design optimisation. Ashby [1] describes how material performance indices (e.g. E/ρ) can help with material selection, for a given design objective such as minimum weight or cost. The selection method can be facilitated using an 'Ashby map', for example plotting E as a function of ρ . The mapping idea can be extended via multiple selection stages, to take into account practical considerations [2]. The methodology developed by Ashby for materials selection provides a conceptual framework for selection of composite structures. The selection methodology can be used to choose between a wide range of variants of the proposed structure, with FE analysis providing the structural performance of the structure. The design selection methodology proposed here is suitable for the early stages of the design process, where the designer considers the widest possible range of solutions that will satisfy the constraints established in the design brief [3,4,5].

Even when the problem is relatively simple, as with the dogbone case study described in this paper, the number of permutations that might be considered can be very large. Particular concerns with design optimisation of composite structures include: a restricted number of ply orientation angles should be considered; ply numbers must be integer; often (but not always) a balanced and symmetric lay-up should be used; several reinforcement regions can be included. When all these factors are taken into account, along with the need to consider

different load cases and design objectives, tailoring the geometry, material properties and layup of the composite laminate to find an optimum design is very challenging [5-8]. The work presented here is an alternative approach to complex / numerical optimisation methods, and is based on the use of 2-D charts to evaluate the laminate's performance [1,2,6,7,9]. The power of the approach lies not only with the simplicity with which lots of data can be visualised, but also the ease with which the designer can interact with the data. This makes it relatively easy to pose 'what-if' questions about changes in the design constraints or objectives and so identify attractive ways of re-formulating the problem.

DESIGN SELECTION METHODOLOGY

In this section we give an overview of the methodology and a step-by-step guide to the procedure. The following section gives a detailed description of how the methodology is implemented in a simple case study.

Overview

The basic idea of the methodology is to consider a very wide range of structural composite designs, perform appropriate calculations, including FE, to determine their performance, incorporate the results into a database, view the data to screen out infeasible solutions or those not meeting the design constraints, and finally identify a shortlist of solutions which best meet the design goals. In essence the method builds on Weaver's methodology for laminate selection [6], but introduces structural analysis into the methodology, recognising the way in which structure and laminate lay-up are closely coupled in composites design.

Ashby's selection method has been implemented in user-friendly software, CES [9], which forms the selection 'engine' of the methodology. Tables of design configurations and corresponding performance data are imported into a database within the software. The designer is then able to exploit the interactive capability of the selection software, to impose appropriate design constraints or selection criteria. To facilitate the process, and to help extract trends from the data, the records have been colour coded by laminate lay-up. Various performance windows shows the appropriate performance measures, such as stiffness or material used. The designer can then use the software to straightforwardly impose constraints and optimise the component. In the case study, performance measures of deflection, cost and maximum strain energy are used to identify a few appropriate lay-ups which fulfil the design requirements while giving the minimum amount of material.

Details of methodology

The procedure followed in the methodology can be shown in a flowchart (Fig. 1). It can be divided in six stages, as follows;

- **Design Brief.** The design brief defines the requirements of the design. This gives as much information as possible on who is going to use the design, how, where and when, etc?
- **Set up the Methodology.** In this stage is important to identify clearly the *constraints*, *variables* and *design objectives* [2]. The information gathered in the design brief must be translated into quantitative constraints (e.g. maximum weight), variables and design objectives (e.g. minimum cost). Here ranges over which the variables can change are set (for example specifying that only 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ ply orientation can be used in the case of laminates). Laminate plate theory is then used to calculate material properties for all possible lay-up combinations.

The design methodology is illustrated by way of a case study. A dogbone specimen is considered, with a series of design constraints to simulate a practical composites design. This case study was chosen as it allows consideration of some key features of composite structures, variable geometry, laminate lay-up and laminate reinforcement. The laminate lay-up is considered to be composed of a primary lay-up, which has the same ply orientations and thickness over the specimen, and secondary reinforcement over part of the structure.

Definition of problem

Geometry and loading

The component, illustrated in Fig. 2a (which shows half of the symmetrical component), is of fixed length and width. Axial and shear loads are applied to the ends of the dogbone as indicated. In this study the radius r of the cut-out is held fixed at a value of 11.67mm. Other work explores the change in radius.

Materials

The specimen is made of unidirectional pre-preg from one of three different materials; E-glass/epoxy (Scotchply/1002), Kevlar/epoxy (Kevlar 49/934) and carbon/epoxy (T300/5208). The properties of these materials can be found in Table 1. The thickness of the plies is 0.125 mm. Only balanced symmetric lay-ups are considered (so that only half the thickness of the specimen need be considered) and only ply orientations of 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ are used.

Primary layup

The total number of plies in the primary lay-up was varied from 4 to 20, which gives a total of 140 different combinations of 0° , 90° and $\pm 45^\circ$ (considering that the laminate has to be balanced and symmetric).

Secondary lay-up (reinforcement)

The specimen is divided into zones where the material reinforcement will be considered, as shown in Fig. 2a. The reinforcement can have as many as 3 plies per half of the laminate and it has to be balanced and symmetric (the same lay-up has to be added to the top and bottom of the laminate). This gives a total of 12 possible reinforcement combinations. Table 3 gives the 12 secondary lay-ups considered. Five different combinations of reinforcements zones are included, as detailed in Table 4.

Table 1. Material properties. (cost are very approximate)

	E_{11} (GPa)	E_{22} (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	Poisson's ratio	Density (kg/m ³)	Cost (£/kg)
E-glass/epoxy (Scotchply/1002)	39	8.3	4.1	0.26	1900	5
Kevlar/Epoxy (Kevlar 49/934)	76	5.5	2.3	0.34	1400	25
Carbon/epoxy (T300/5208)	181	10.3	7.17	0.28	1500	100

Design objectives

The design objectives which are considered in the problem are: weight, cost, deflection at the top-left node A due to the applied load, and maximum strain energy density within the specimen. This latter objective is used as a simple way to model failure. The deflection and the strain energy density are extracted from the FE output file for each run. The weight is calculated by finding the surface area of the part and multiplying it by the thickness and the density of the material. The cost is calculated by multiplying the mass of the component with the cost of the material per unit mass. The model cost used in this paper is for comparison purposes only and to include the cost as a design variable. For a more accurate cost of the part a more complex model needs to be used, such as those described in [10,11,12].

Fig. 2 Dog-bone case study: (a) geometry; (b) finite element model

The design constraints, variables and objectives used in the case study are summarised in Table 2. Considering the 140 combinations for the basic lay-up, the 12 possible combinations for the secondary lay-up and the five different reinforcement cases, we end up with 6860 independent cases for each material. With three different materials being considered, the number of independent cases increases to 20,580.

Table 2. Constraints, variables and objectives.

Constraints	<i>Geometric:</i> Fixed length and width. <i>Loading:</i> Fixed shear and axial load. <i>Lay-up:</i> Balanced, symmetric, 0, 45 and 90° plies only
Variables:	Thickness of waisted region (not changed in this study) Material (CFRP, glass fibre, Kevlar) Ply orientations and thicknesses in different regions.
Objectives:	Weight, cost, deflection, strain energy density.

Performance calculations and finite element analysis

A two dimensional finite element model of the component was generated in MSC.Marc, as shown in Fig. 2b. The tension and shear components of the pressure loading applied to the left-hand end of the component were 100 N/m, while symmetric boundary conditions were applied at the right-hand end. The model takes between 1 and 2 seconds to run. In the FE model, the materials were treated as 2D orthotropic materials, changing the stiffness properties (E_x , E_y , G_{xy} and ν_{xy}) and the thickness of the material elements according to the lay-up, including any reinforcement. The stiffness matrix of the material was obtained using

laminates plate theory [7,13,14]. Each of the 20,580 possible designs was analysed using FE, to give the maximum strain energy density and displacement at node A.

Table 3. Secondary lay-ups

Reinforcement combination	Secondary Lay-up
1	[±45]s
2	[90]s
3	[90/±45]s
4	[90 ₂]s
5	[90 ₃]s
6	[0]s
7	[0/±45]s
8	[0/90]s
9	[0/90 ₂]s
10	[0 ₂]s
11	[0 ₂ /90]s
12	[0 ₃]s

Fig. 3 Structure of the Database

Table 4. Reinforcements zones.

Reinforcement case	Zones reinforced
0	No reinforcement
1	Zones 3 – 4
2	Zones 2 – 3
3	Zones 4 – 5
4	Zones 2 – 3 – 4 – 5

Performance plots

The results were used to build a database, which was created with a tree structure as shown in Fig. 3, adopting the idea of a tree structure used for the materials database of CES. Going from the general to the particular the structure consists of: a) Composites, b) Material (prepregs, CFRP, E-glass, Kevlar), c) Number of plies in the basic lay-up (from 4 to 20 plies), d) Possible ply combination to create a symmetric and balanced laminate with that number of plies, e) Reinforcement combinations (secondary lay-up) and finally, f) Reinforcement case (where a secondary lay-up is included).

With this database it is possible to create 2-D charts to compare the laminate's performance. The results for the 20,580 independent cases are shown in Fig. 4. With the tree structure established in the data base, it is straightforward to confirm from Fig 4b what we already knew, that E-glass (pink) will be the cheapest solution, then Kevlar (blue), and finally carbon fibre will be the most expensive solution, but also the one with the best mechanical properties per unit mass. But also, from Fig. 4a, it can be seen that the Kevlar solution is fine where the displacement constraint is not too small. Some Kevlar solutions have displacements less than 0.5 mm and while there is not a significant increase in weight compared to carbon fibre specimens, there is a huge cost saving. The designer can readily see that, if the deflection restraint can be relaxed a little, choosing a Kevlar specimens will save a substantial amount of money (though it is important to remember that the cost model used is very simple, and the use of a different cost model may lead to different results).

Fig. 4 Selection charts (complete set of results, colour code: pink = E-glass, blue = Kevlar and red = carbon fibre): (a) mass - deflection; (b) cost – strain energy

Now, looking only at the results for one material (carbon fibre, for example), and setting a different colour for each number of plies, as shown in Fig 5, a well-defined column for each colour can be seen. In the same way, plotting the maximum strain energy as a function of the cost shows a similar columnar pattern. This is due to the fact that the cost is directly related with the weight and there are no penalties for the use of reinforcements. But also, using this colour code, it can be seen that, for the load pattern applied, the use of 14 or more plies would increase the weight (and the cost) of the specimen without adding any substantial gain in the displacement (nor in the strain energy). On the other hand, it can be seen, for example, that a cheap and light solution of 4 plies $[\pm 45]_s$ with a reinforcement of $[0_2]_s$ applied in zones 2, 3, 4 and 5 can be used, if we decide not to use 90 degree plies.

In summary, by using a tree structure and plotting the results with colour codes, for example by reinforcement combination or reinforcement case, the selection software can extract useful trends or patterns that may exist in the results. In addition, appropriate constraints can be imposed to narrow the possibilities and search for the best solution, as illustrated in the next section.

Fig. 5 Selection charts (carbon fibre); mass - deflection

Selection

In practical design, there will often be constraints which need to be applied to the design, perhaps arising from mechanical considerations or manufacturing. Here we show how these can be applied in an interactive way by the designer. The selection software allows the designer to highlight areas on the performance plots within which the points must fall. For example, a box drawn in Fig. 6a imposes upper limits on the allowable deflection and mass. Because the various performance charts plotting the performance parameters are linked, points lying outside the selected area on one selection chart are greyed-out on all the graphs. In other words, where different areas are selected on several graphs, only points passing all the selection criteria will remain coloured, as illustrated in Fig. 6b.

To illustrate how this can be used, we include in the fictional design brief the following four design constraints:

- Cost \leq £3
- Mass \leq 40g
- Displacement (at the top corner) \leq 2mm
- Maximum strain energy $\leq 2 \times 10^6$ N/m²

When the data are represented graphically and the above constraints applied to the graphs (Figs. 6a and 6b) the number of cases is reduced to 3325. It would then be straightforward to identify suitable designs from these charts minimising mass or cost, which meet all the constraints. However, to illustrate the flexibility of the selection method, consider applying additional constraints, perhaps arising from manufacturing considerations:

- The laminate must be quasi-isotropic
- Reinforcement is applied only in zones 3 and 4, if at all (reinforcement cases 0 or 1).
- A maximum of one extra ply for reinforcement per half laminate.

Applying these additional constraints gives only 38 possibilities as shown in Fig 6c and 6d. Of these 38, six correspond to E-glass, six to CFRP and the remaining 26 to Kevlar. All of

these points have a laminate lay-up $[0,90,\pm 45]_s$ and have one or no reinforcement plies in zones 3 and 4 only. The optimal solution for each material has been found from the mass vs. deflection graph, as highlighted in fig 6c. These same points have then been highlighted in fig 6d. In Figs. 6c and 6d, the cases that do not meet the constraints are not shown to aid visualisation.

Fig. 6 Selection charts (complete set of results, colour code: pink = E-glass, blue = Kevlar and red = carbon fibre): (a) mass - deflection; (b) cost - strain energy (c) Optimum results; mass - deflection; (d) Optimum results; cost - strain energy

CONCLUDING DISCUSSION

A simple design methodology has been developed, based on a methodology for material selection, to optimise composite structures. The method uses finite element analysis to identify the mechanical response of a range of proposed designs, and commercial selection software to impose appropriate constraints and choose between conflicting design objectives. The method is ideally suited to more complex composite structures. Work is in hand to include manufacturing constraints via a draping analysis. For these more complicated problems it is envisaged that an exhaustive search of the design space will not be feasible.

Instead genetic algorithms will be used to generate a diverse population of proposed structures.

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